

PROFITABILITY DRIVERS OF LISTED AGRIBUSINESS FIRMS IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE OF MACROAND FIRM-SPECIFIC EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the macro and firm-specific effects on profitability of agribusinesses listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange from 2015 to 2023 as result of firm hazards that dominate the economy. Profitability was proxy by Net Profit Margin (NPM). Databases of World Bank, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletins; and audited annual financials of the selected agribusinesses were sourced for macro and firm- specific levels data respectively. Data were analyzed using traditional panel models, and specifically with Fixed Effects improved with Driscoll-Kraay Standard estimator (DKSE). Despite Random Effects model being preferred by standard Hausman Test, a better model of Fixed Effects improved with Driscoll-Kraay Standard estimator (DKSE) was adopted for results reporting. Findings show that bank credit, interest rate and liquidity have positive and significant effects on NPM. Also, firm size has a negative and statistically significant effect on NPM. Economic policy uncertainty, inflation rate, exchange rate, age and firm leverage have insignificant and varied effects on NPM. The findings underscore the importance of firm resource use policies that ensure consistent and sustained net profit margin of agribusinesses. Also, dynamic policies of financial deepening, with interest rate policy moderation that could improve agribusinesses profitability should be prioritized by policymakers to improve profitability of agribusinesses in Nigeria.

JEL Codes: Q00; Q1; Q13; L66

1. INTRODUCTION

A new paradigm shift of transforming primary agriculture to agribusiness for a market-driven economy is contemporarily policy construct in emerging economies. Nigeria as emerging economy is mostly agrarian that has reduced agriculture's contribution to GDP when compared with the oil sector. Macroeconomic instability calls for economic diversification with agribusiness growth model to ensure economic growth and development. Adeyemi and Adewole, (2017); Muhammed, *et al.* (2020); and Oloni, *et al.* (2017) agreed that economic diversification of Nigeria economy may come from agriculture as it stabilizes the economy that mainly depends on oil revenue.

Transformation of agriculture to agribusiness implies profit making. Sustained profits (profitability) attract entrepreneurs, corporate organizations, international partners and investors to agribusiness market environment. Thus, Adeyeye (2017) opine that agribusiness diversification could lead an increased export, income generation, job creation, and sustainable food security in Nigeria.

From the supply side, agribusiness creates and amplifies employment through grass root creativity and innovations in linkages of agribusiness value chains. On this note, Dorosh and Thurhow, (2018) opined that poverty reduction through agribusiness can be more pronounced except in few cases of manufacturing firms that have an agribusiness undertone. Importantly, security of food and reduced post-harvest losses of perishable agricultural produce is a significant role of agribusiness (Qange, Mdoda, and Mditshwa (2024). And contribution of agribusiness to the GDP of economies has been empirically documented by Aldona and Agnieszka (2016) and Medina (2022). Thus, economic diversification from agribusiness growth model can sustained economic growth and development in emerging rural economies of sub-Saharan Africa in the recent times.

Further, the demand side of agribusiness role include increase demand of food with varied tastes by the surging population. Making agriculture profitable can increase farm productivity at micro-levels. Moreover, the capitalistic economic system of emerging economies could lead agribusiness to market-driven thereby bridging the gap of demand and supply side. Agribusiness value addition and value chain reduces post-harvest losses, it spurs creativity and innovation bringing forth novelty in agricultural sector. Thus, agribusiness role in food security is important and commercialization of the entire agribusiness system makes food available and accessible in the economy.

In corporate agribusiness, the margins of profits at the end of financial year is very important. It signals the strength and vulnerability of firms in times of macroeconomic fluctuations in emerging economies. Importantly, the paucity of empirical evidence and relevance of net profit margin in agribusiness firm's performance studies in emerging economies especially in Nigeria is underestimated. Macroeconomic and firm- level studies in Nigeria focus mainly in financial and other sectors with less empirical studies specifically on agribusiness. Also, the need to account for cross-sectional dependence among firms in a macro and firm-specific studies is important in making inferences in corporate agribusiness study.

In recent decade, hazard of firms in Nigeria market environment is alarming. Sobowale (2024) noted that within five years of 2020 to 2024, over 20 firms have either shut down or left Nigeria market to another economy. This hazard could have arisen from recorded slight margins of net profits of sales among the firms that may not be able to withstand macroeconomic fluctuations irrespective of their internal resources. For instance, the shock of persistent inflation can remove the liquidity base of a firm, and inflation is usually co-mover with other macroeconomic variables such as interest rate and even exchange rate. Thus, both macro and firm-level variables effect can have compound and pronounced effects on profit per unit sale of firms making net profit margins indeterminate especially in unstable and emerging economies like Nigeria. Therefore, this study unravels the effects of macro and micro-level effects on net profit margin of listed agribusinesses in Nigeria, and provided an econometric comparison with different traditional panel models.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Macroeconomics are aggregations of micro economic variables arising from actions of individual economic agents in an economic system and as such, have a cumulative effect on the whole economy. The instability of these variables results in macroeconomic volatilities. Economic policy uncertainty, bank credit issues, exchange rate, inflation and interest rates are some macroeconomic variables of importance that could affect corporate agribusiness. The etymology of the word 'macroeconomics' comes from Greek origin- 'makro' meaning 'large' (Egbunike and Okerekeoti (2018); while, 'oikos' means 'household', and 'nomia' meaning 'management' (Leshem, 2016). Thus, the influence of macroeconomic variables shapes economies and its impact on listed agribusinesses cannot be overemphasized in emerging market economies.

Economic Policy Uncertainty

Economic policy uncertainty is an aspect of uncertainty in policy making in economic affairs that shows the level of preparedness by political elites. Quddus *et al.* (2021) sees economic policy uncertainty as a hazard that is related to government policy instability that can introduce uncertainty in potential policies and regulatory structure. This injects uncertainty in managerial decision-making and could adversely affect firms in diverse ways. Uncertainty of economic policy can affect firms by either increasing or decreasing their profitability.

Exchange Rate

All emerging economies of sub-Saharan Africa is market-driven and are in constant exchange with other economies. Exchange economy is a new paradigm of global trade and competitiveness which implies that trading nations' currencies be exchanged (swapped) for either export or import of goods and services. Thus, the rate at which this exchange is done is known as exchange rate (forex) system. Hence, Moyo and Tursoy (2020) defined it as the value of a country's currency against another country. Extant studies have varied effects of exchange rate effects on firms especially in agribusiness and related sectors.

Inflation Rate

Inflation is a persistent macroeconomic variable that face all market economies. It is a co-mover variable that it can alter the entire economic system reshaping it and having influences on other macroeconomics variables. It is defined as generalized increase in price level sustained over a long period of time. Toprr (2022) reported that inflation can affect an economy in both ways – positive or negative depending on the accelerator. Thus, its effects on profitability could be in positive or negative depending on type of agribusiness activities and among others.

Interest Rate

Resources have alternative uses. When resource is used, it creates wealth and adds value to the system. Interest is an opportunity cost of lending out resources which would have added value to the owner's wealth. Therefore, borrower must pay interest for the use of external fund for business. The frequency of payment of the accrued charges from the use of funds is 'interest rate'. Hence, Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) (2016) defined interest rate as the amount charged on borrowed fund, expressed as percentage of the principal by the lender of such to the borrower of the said fund for its use. The amount, the interval of payment is at the discretion of the lender, and prevailing macroeconomic indices could affect agribusiness' profitability.

Bank Credit

Resources that could finance agribusinesses are many but bank credit is the money that financial institutions lend to the public at the dictates of the apex bank. The monetary policies of the Central Bank could favor or limit money in circulation thereby constricting available fund for agribusiness firms. Thus, Thakur (2020) defined bank credit as disbursed loan backed with or without collateral which is expected to earn periodic interest. Its' use in agribusinesses increases the financial base of the firm and could encourage major investment and diversification to useful linkages characteristic of agribusinesses which could results in higher profits.

Firm- Specific Characteristics

Firm-specific characteristics are firms' internal, intrinsic, identifier, peculiarity, marks and other identities that distinguishes firm from each other. Localization of firms is possible for similar firms but identities differ in terms of size, age, liquidity position and leverage status.

Age

The time of establishment of firm is its age and sometimes it may not coincide with the inception of business, and its incorporation date may be entirely different. The effect of age in agribusiness is often in positive terms a priori. Firms exhibit living characteristics and are subject to growth and decline with attendant benefits and consequences. Studies have shown that as firm advance in age, its performance may have either advantages or disadvantages. Thus, Ofuan and Izien (2016) proved that age's learning by doing hypothesis has a positive relationship with profitability of listed firms in Nigeria Stock market as at 2014.

Size

Size of firm can influence its profitability. Size could mean physical assets of the firm or the size of employees. In either way, size of firm can have positive or negative effects on profitability if not properly managed. Recently, the rise of automation is reducing the number of employees but productivity is still sustained. Therefore, size is important firm attributes that can influence profitability especially in emerging economies that have fewer stable firms and surging start-ups that are prone to hazards. Thus, its use in financial studies is important (Kioko, 2013).

Liquidity

Agribusiness firms set resources aside for every business year. This is the working capital and the rate at which these resources are easily converted to cash and cash equivalents for daily operation is known as 'liquidity'. Nanda and Panda (2018) posit that excess liquidity in form of current assets could to high maintenance costs and may reduce profitability. Also, shortage of liquidity during the business operation could lead to liquidity trap and that could be disastrous to firm's profitability.

Leverage

Leverage is an important internal metrics of listed agribusiness firms that imply using external debts to finance the firms' productions and operations. It refers to the proportion of debt-to-equity shares of the owners in the capital structure of a firm (Omondi and Muturi, 2013). It strives to measure what portion of the total assets is financed by debt funds. Borrowed funds can either have positive or negative effects on profitability depending on terms and conditions on the fund. Importantly, is the need to emphasize the effect of high fixed cost on the firm that will amount to high accruals in adverse macroeconomic influences.

The conceptual framework is described below:

Figure 1. Conceptual Diagram

Source: Authors' model.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The underpinning profitability theory to this study is focused on resource-based view/theory (RBV) propounded by Penrose in 1959 and developed by Wernerfelt in 1984 (Olarewaju and Msomi, 2022). The resource-based theory emphasizes on the power of firms in generating profits using their resources. This theory underscores the casual link of competitive advantage of firms over another as the basis for profit making. Thus, firms that have strategic potentials and resources are likely to have more competitive advantage thereby being profitable than another firm that have less resources (Egbunike and Okerekeoti, 2018). This implies that the determinants of profitability of these firms are depended on the micro-level characteristics (internal firm focus) of the firms and thus, distinct from other similar firms in the same industry, hence, differential profitability. Thus, the theory asserts that the firms' micro-level characteristics do significantly affect the profitability of the listed agribusinesses.

Another similar theoretical underpinning to this study is the Open Systems Theory propounded by Bertalanffy in 1950 and 1968 which states that organizations operate in an open systems with continuous interaction with external (macro) environment. Katz and Kahn (1966) first applied this theory to firm stating that firms exist by importing inputs and transforming them. On so doing, their activities are significantly affected by macroeconomic fluctuations accounting for profitability differentials. Firms react to macroeconomic variables in the economy thereby adjusting to reduce the adverse effects that may affect profits in their business activities. Therefore, firms must contend with macroeconomic forces, micro-level variables to sustain and remain profitable. This theory is linked to the present study with the null hypothesis that the dynamics of macroeconomics variables in the economy do not significantly affect profitability.

2.3 Empirical Review

Listed agribusinesses experience continuous macroeconomic fluctuations that shape their profitability. These macroeconomic variables fluctuation are external and out of their control (Cheong and Hoang (2021)). These fluctuations determine mainly profitability (Net Profit Margin) of listed agribusiness firms.

Extant studies such as Akenroye *et al.* (2022) opine that firm's attributes have joint significant effect on Net Profit Margin and with firm size as an attribute it drives financial performance. As a measure of profitability- the Gross Profit Margin, and Net Profit Margin together affect the value of the company as reviewed by Mulyadi *et al* (2020) which found that NPM influences increasing firm value and has a strong relationship with firm value as proxies by Tobin's Q. As an independent factor on profit growth, Handayani and Winarningsih (2020) noted that NPM statistically affected the profit growth on Food and Beverage firms listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange within 2016-2019.

Also, as a co-factor on determining financial distress of goods and consumption sector of manufacturing firms listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange, Indrati and Putri (2021) noted that NPM has a significant influence in determining the financial distress of firms and specifically pushes firms to economic desperation. Weidman *et al.* (2019) found that NPM has a positive effect on ROE of firms. Wang and Wu (2020) found out that NPM has no significant effect on initial public offer (IPO) underpricing. And Sofronas *et al* (2020) noted that NPM has a positive and significant effect on Tobin Q of firms. Continuing, Chaudhry *et al* (2020) proxies many management variables' effect on NPM and found that audit committee chair experimental expertise (ACCEE), nomination committee chair human resource expertise (NCCHRE), and firm size has no significant effect on NPM; audit committee chair financial expertise (ACCFE), audit committee chair monitoring expertise (ACCME), nomination committee chair experimental expertise (NCCEE) and firm size have a significant and positive effect on NPM, while board size has negative and significant effect on NPM. While using NPM as independent variable on ROE of firm profitability, Weidman *et al* (2019) noted that NPM has positive and significant effect on return on equity. Killingsworth and Mehany (2018) reported that NPM has a significant effect on gross profit of firms.

Research and development could be an indicator of firm's progress/ performance. Zhou *et al.* (2019) noted that NPM has a negative and significant effect on research and development. Przychodzen and Przychodzen (2018) noted that NPM has a positive and significant effect on sustainable innovations which could be resultant effect of research and development. Conclusively, Wuku (2021) opine that NPM could affect or be affected by firm-specific factors while, Renet *al.* (2021) found that COVID- 19 as a macroeconomic variable can affect NPM with the report of Mucharreira *et al.* (2019) who revealing that tourism affect NPM in hotel industry.

Choiriyah *et al.* (2021) reported that NPM among other variables have significant effects on stock prices of banking firms listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, but specifically noted that, the coefficient of NPM and ROA don't have any significant effect on the stockprice of the listed firms. Nevertheless, ROE and EPS significantly affect the stock price of the listed firms. Rahman *et al.* (2020) found that advertising intensity has a positive and insignificant effect on NPM. Akenroye, *et al.* (2022) found that asset tangibility investment has a positive and insignificant effect on NPM

attributes and financial performance of quoted companies in Nigeria, although, the variable.s proxy is different and with different firms in the same economy. Mimouni, *et al.*(2019) found a negative and significant effect of sukuk on NPM of conventional and Islamic banks. Tee (2019) found that total institutional investor among other explanatory variables have significant and positive effect on NPM for institutional investors’ investment preference and monitoring research in Malaysia. Pervan and Pervan (2017) found a statistically significant and negative relationship between age’s influences on performance proxy as EBITDA Margin of Croatian food industry.

Nariswari and Nugraha (2020) found that NPM has a significant and positive effect on growth of plastic and packaging industry in Indonesia between 2014-2018periods. Also, Supriyadi (2021) noted a positive and statistically influence on firm value in Indonesia. Ramadahan and Nuraliati (2020) conclude that a significant effect is found between NPM and stock prices of food and beverage firms in the country and at the same period.

3. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive and three tradional panel data regression models were used to analyze the data. The Fixed effects augmented with Driscoll-Kraay estimator was the fourth model as it accounts among others, cross-sectional dependence and robustness checks. Thus, Fixed Effects model augmented with Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors (DKSE) was selected on discretion despite its’ insignificance on Hausman specification test. The study purposively selected 18 agribusiness firms listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange from 2015 to 2023 for the reason of having complete audited annual financial reports (see Table 1-Definition of variables, data sources and measurements).

Table 1. Names of firms, definition of variables, data sources and measurement

Dependent Variable	Definition & Measurement of Variable	Source of Data
Net Profit Margin (NPM)	Net profit margin is computed as net profit after tax divided by sales revenue (expressed as a percentage)	Annual financial reports of the firms available on the firms’ website.
Independent Variables	(Macroeconomics)	
Economic Policy uncertainty (EPU)	Economic policy uncertainty, which is measured using the global economic policy uncertainty index for Nigeria.	Baker, Bloom and Davis (2016), https://www.policyuncertainty.com/all_country_data.html .
Exchange rate (EXR)	Official Naira to Dollar exchange rate, period average	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (2024). https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators ; CBN (2021).
Inflation Rate (INF)	Inflation rate, measured using	World Bank’s World Development Indicators https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators .

		annual inflation rate (%)	
Bank Credit (BCR)	Credit	Bank credit is measured using domestic credit to private sector by banks (% of GDP)	World Bank. (2025). <i>World Development Indicators: Domestic credit to private sector (% of GDP) in Nigeria, 2010–2022</i> . https://databank.worldbank.org/id/8a631e35
Interest rate (INTR)	rate	Interest rate, measured using lending interest rate (%)	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (2024). https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators .
Independent Variables (Firm-Specific)			
Firm Age (AGE)	Age	Firm age is measured as the number of years of existence of the firm	Annual financial reports of the firms available on the firms’ website
Firm Size (SIZE)	Size	Firm size is measured as the total assets	Annual financial reports of the firms available on the firms’ website
Firm Liquidity (LIQ)	Liquidity	Firm liquidity is measured using the current ratio, that is, current assets divided by current liabilities (expressed as a percentage)	Annual financial reports of the firms available on the firms’ website
Firm Leverage (LEV)	Leverage	Firm leverage is computed as total debt divided by total assets (expressed as a percentage)	Annual financial reports of the firms available on the firms’ website

Source: Authors’ compilation.

Selected agribusiness firm’s name.

Dangote Sugar Plc., 2. Nigeria Brewery Plc., 3. Guinness Plc., 4. Champion Brewery Plc., 5. International Brewery Plc., 6. Nestle Nigeria Plc., 7. FTN Cocoa., 8. Livestock Plc., 9. Northern Nigeria Flour Plc., 10. Cadbury Plc., 11., Honeywell Nigeria Plc., 12. Flour Mill Nig.plc., 13. Notore Nig. Plc., 14. Okomuo Oil Plc., 15. NASCON Plc., 16. PZ Cussons Plc., 17. PRESCO Plc., & 18. McNicholls Plc.

3.1 Model Specification

The study followed the functional form of the panel model as specified by Odusanya *et al.* (2018) and; Nanda and Panda (2018).

The functional model implicit is:

$$NPM_{it} = f(EPU_{it}, EXR_{it}, INF_{it}, BCR_{it}, INTR_{it}, AGE_{it}, SIZE_{it}, LIQ_{it}, LEV_{it}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The explicit Econometric model:

$$NPM = \alpha_i + \beta_1 EPU_{it} + \beta_2 EXR_{it} + \beta_3 INF_{it} + \beta_4 BCR_{it} + \beta_5 INTR_{it} + \beta_6 AGE_{it} + \beta_7 SIZE_{it} + \beta_8 LIQ_{it} + \beta_9 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where: *NPM* = net profit margin (proxy of profitability).

EPU = economic policy uncertainty; (an index (No.)); *EXR* = exchange rate;(₦); *INF* =inflation rate;(‰); *BCR*=bank credit;(‰) ; *INTR* = interest rate;(‰); *AGE* = firm age; (yrs); *SIZE* = firm size; (total assets); *LIQ*= firm liquidity; (‰);firm *LEV* = leverage; (‰) *i* = the *i*th firm;*t* = the time period.

The null hypotheses tested were:

H₀₁= economic policy uncertainty does not affect net profit margin; H₀₂= exchange rate does not affect net profit margin;H₀₃= inflation rate does not affectnet profit margin; H₀₄= bank credit do not affectnet profit margin; H₀₅= interest rate does not affectnet profit margin; H₀₆= firm age does not affectnet profit margin; H₀₇= firm size does not affectnet profit margin; H₀₈= firm liquidity does not affectnet profit margin; H₀₉ = firm leverage does not affectnet profit margin.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hausman Test

Hausman specification test shows that random effects model is preferred over other traditional panel models. Table 2 presents the result of the test under the assumption of null hypothesis which states that the random effects model is preferred. The p-value (.142) is insignificant, but fixed effects was selected based on the significance level of cross-sectional test in Table 3 to avoid the violation of cross-sectional dependence assumptions, and to account for the heterogeneity across the selected firms. Essentially, the random effects assume that the cross-sectional units are independent and also, that the error terms are uncorrelated across units while cross-sectional dependence implies that units are correlated with each other. With the presence of cross-sectional dependence in Table 3, adopting random effects model may lead to biased standard errors and invalid inference. Therefore, the use of fixed effects models with Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors is justified because it gives robustness to the estimates being an option for panel model of short-term time-series with larger number of cross-sectional units. Also, the choice of fixed effects model with Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors will eliminate the biases of random effects model, and also accounts for the heterogeneity and temporal dependence among the selected firms. Thus, the study relied more on the Fixed Effects Model with Driscoll-Kraay to discuss the results of the findings of the study.

Table 2. Hausman (1978) Specification Test to choose between FE and RE Model

Model	X ² Statistics	Df	P-value	Decision
NPM	6.633	9	.142	RE preferred

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis (Random Effects) at p<0.05. Source: Authors’ computation.

Cross-Sectional Dependence Tests

The cross-sectional dependence test as proposed by Pesaran (2021), Friedman (1937) and Frees (1995) is presented in Table 3 below and shows that cross-sectional dependence is present- (see Frees’ Test value). Cross- sectional dependence assumes that error terms affecting a firm may be affecting others firms in the same economic system. Thus, the choice of Fixed Effects estimator augmented with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors was adopted for the present study as against the Random effects which assumes that the firms are entirely independent from one another. The use of fixed effect also takes care of time –invariant variables so that the net effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable could be estimated.

Table 3. Cross-sectional Dependence Test Results

Test	Statistics	Critical value	P-value	Conclusion
Pesaran CD	-1.482	-	0.1382	No dependence
Frees	0.562**	0.3826	-	Dependence
Friedman	2.874	-	0.9999	No dependence

Conclusion: Presence of cross-sectional dependence. Source: Authors’ computation.

Correlation

Independent variables collinearity is computed to check the presence of collinearity. Collinearity exists when the pair wise correlation between any pair of regressors is equal to or above 0.80 (Gujarati and Porter (2009). Table 4 presents the pair wise correlation matrix of the study’s independent variables and it showed low to moderate correlations. However, a high correlation of 0.853 was noticed between exchange rate and inflation rate suggesting evidence of multicollinearity. This poses no such risk as no other strong correlation was detected as seen in the table.

Table 4 . Pair wise logged correlation matrix of independent variables

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1)LEPU	1.000								
(2)LEXR	0.686	1.000							
(3)LINFL	0.434	0.853	1.000						
(4)LBCR	-0.158	0.396	0.660	1.000					
(5)LINTR	-0.635	-0.643	-0.467	-0.069	1.000				
(6)LAGE	0.115	0.135	0.101	0.026	-0.116	1.000			
(7)LSIZE	0.149	0.235	0.200	0.092	-0.169	-0.156	1.000		
(8)LLIQ-	-0.009	0.050	0.060	0.076	-0.027	0.072	-0.030	1.000	
(9)LLEV	0.301	0.306	0.236	0.063	-0.239	0.078	0.075	-0.382	1.000

Source: Author’s computation using STATA 17.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 5 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. There were 162 observations for each variable, which reflects the availability of data for each of the 18 selected agribusiness firms from 2015 to 2023. The mean shows the average recorded for each variable while the standard deviation records the variability of the estimate during the study period. The minimum and maximum values indicate the lowest and highest record observed by each variable. For instance, the mean value is reported at 40.509 and implies that agribusiness firms on average earned ₦40.509 as NPM per revenue in the business during the period of study. The maximum and minimum net profit margin of the agribusiness firms are also shown to be ₦1481.265 and ₦.092 respectively. The standard deviation of 158.255 indicates variability within the mean.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mini.	Max.
NPM	162	40.509	158.255	.092	1481.265
EPU	162	220.577	58.053	121.088	320.886
EXR.	162	355.096	122.968	192.44	645.194
INFL.	162	15.378	4.408	9.009	24.66
BCR.	162	12.775	2.155	10.18	17.586
INTR.	162	15.002	2.101	11.483	17.553
AGE	162	44.469	18.847	9	77
SIZE	162	1.776e+08	2.086e+08	1739760	1.069e+09
LIQ.	162	147.136	420.837	7.291	5364.565
LEV.	162	66.117	47.223	2.59	592.013

Source: Author's computation using STATA 17.

Table 6. Regression Estimates of Variables of FE with DKSE, FE, RE and Pooled OLS

Variable	FE+DSKE	FE	RE	OLS
LEPU	0.015(0.200)	.015(.401)	.059(.395)	-.112(.715)
LEXR	0.579(0.415)	.579(.734)	.738(.707)	.7(1.034)
LINFL	0.252(0.184)	.252(.962)	.19(.96)	.183(1.012)
LBCR	0.470(0.218) *	.47(1.054)	.468(1.062)	.539(1.175)
LINTR	1.219(0.177) ***	1.219(.473) **	1.059(.441) **	1.015(1.09)
LAGE	0.405(0.627)	.405(1.447)	-.884(.348) **	-1.038(.157) ***
LSIZE	-0.329(0.117) **	.329(.198)	-.234(.164)	-.191(.09) **
LLIQ	0.299(0.062) ***	.299(.191)	.23(.203)	-.217(.196)
LLEV	-0.085 (0.091)	-.085(.201)	-.05(.187)	.313(.292)
CONSTANT	-3.134	-3.134	-.516	.917
R ²	0.1192	0.119	0.105	0.194
F-statistics	181.15(0.0000)	8.759 (0.000)	(0.000)	5.554 (0.000)
Observations	162	162	162	162

Notes: Standard errors in parentheses. ***, **, * denote significance at 1%, 5% and 10%.

Source: Author's computation using STATA 17.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The regression estimates using the Fixed Effects model with Driscoll-Kraay Standard Errors in addition with traditional panel models of Fixed Effects, Random Effects and Pooled OLS is presented in Table 6 above.

The result from Table 6 shows that the coefficient of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) on net profit margin of the selected agribusiness firms is 0.015 with an insignificant p-value of 0.943. Thus, economic policy uncertainty has a positive effect on net profit margin of the selected agribusiness firms and an increase in uncertainty of economic policy will result in an increase on net profit margin of the selected agribusiness. This aligns with the open systems theoretical underpinning of the study that postulates that firms operate in an open economic environment where they contend with macroeconomic issues such as uncertainty of economic policies. Delay or timely EPU will make firm's management to make more profits or losses. This finding aligns with the findings of Miba'am (2025) which found that global economic uncertainty has a positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria at the middle and upper quantile, but indicated a negative relationship at a lower quantile.

The coefficient of exchange rate is 0.579 with attendant p-value of 0.200. This is a positive relationship, though, insignificant, but implies that as exchange rate increase, the NPM of the selected agribusiness will also increase simultaneously. Exchange rate increases on NPM is usually associated with agribusiness firms that deals with international trade. This finding is in support of the findings of Ajibogun *et al.*(2025) which found that exchange rate at the short-run positively and insignificantly affects industrial production in Nigeria, although in different sector of the same economy.

Inflation rate from Table 6 has a coefficient of 0.252 with p-value of 0.207 which implies that the variable's effect on NPM is positive and insignificant. This shows that inflation rate exerts an increase effect on NPM of the selected agribusiness firms. Inflation rate may actually increase NPM in temporarily and in absolute terms as at the persistent inflation rates may reduce financial gains and even may not translate to financial strength. The finding is in contrary with the findings of Okoye (2022) which showed that inflation has a negative and insignificant effect on return on assets (profitability indicator) of deposit money banks in Nigeria which is also ancillary to agribusiness firms.

Bank credit coefficient is 0.470 with a p-value of 0.064. This shows that bank credit has a positive and statistically significant effect on NPM at 10%. When firms access funds, they invest, expand their production capacity and achieve economies of scale. This reduces production costs, reduces price per unit product, and increases more sales. This increases the net profit margin from the turnover as result of increased sale. Therefore, increase in bank credit will increase the net profit of agribusinesses. This finding is consistent with the findings of Chijioke and Ogugbue (2025) which found that credit from microfinance banks significantly affect profitability of small-scale businesses in Calabar municipality. Also, the finding aligns with the findings of Bello, *et al.* (2021) which found that bank credit has a positive and significant on output of manufacturing sector at the long-run in Nigeria. The finding contradicts the findings of Mimouni, *et al.* (2019) which found a negative and significant effect of sukuk on NPM performance of conventional and Islamic banks, which is ancillary to agribusinesses.

Table 6 shows that interest rate has a positive coefficient of 1.219 with a highly significant p-value of 0.000. The implication is that an increase in interest rate will increase NPM. This finding seems paradoxical as an increase in interest rate should increase the burden of firms to periodically pay back borrowed funds thereby reducing profits. At the same time, it seems plausible as the economy during that periods was expanding after recovering from two economic recessions. Importantly, the positive effects of inflation rate on NPM as suggested by the study in this period shows that the economy is liquid and firms are making profits irrespective of the interest accrued. Nevertheless, moderation of interest rate is needed by the controlling authority (CBN) to avoid imminent chaos in the economy. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Tee (2019), despite using different proxy variables found that total institutional investor have a significant and positive effect on NPM in Malaysia institutional investors' investment preference and monitoring research.

The coefficient of age is 0.405 and the p-value is 0.537, implying insignificant effect on NPM. Despite the relationship being insignificant, the positive coefficient with NPM connotes that as age of firm increases, NPM increases. Agribusinesses should be sustained by innovations and diversification of investment that incorporates forward and backward linkages that could help them

to last a longer period as seen in developed climes. The finding is similar to findings of Akenroye, *et al.* (2022) which found that age has positive and insignificant effect on NPM on firms' attributes and financial performance of quoted companies in Nigeria, but is contrary with findings of Pervan and Pervan (2017) which found a statistically significant and negative relationship between age's influences on performance proxy as EBITDA Margin of Croatian food industry.

The Table 6 shows that size have a coefficient and p-value of -0.329 and 0.023 respectively. This is negative and statistically significant at 5% p-value. Obviously, increase in size of the selected firms will decrease the net profit margin of the firms and could be detrimental to the firms. The decrease of NPM as result of firm's size should be cautionary but could be rational. For instance, firm size measured by number of employees should streamline the workforce and invest on authomated systems that could be multi-tasking but maintained by experienced experts. When firm size is proxy by the assets, management should prioritize among others, regular assets audits to dispose obsolete assets and maintained prudency on assets acqusition. This finding is in opposite to the findings of Akernroye *et al.* (2022) which found that company size status has positive and significant effect on NPM on firms' attributes and financial performance of quoted companies in Nigeria.

The coefficient and p-value of liquidity in Table 6, is 0.299 and 0.001 respectively.. Liquidity signals the ability of firms to meet the financial obligation at short-term and inability to meet this obligation consistently at short-term business cycle could affect the margin of profit per sale. Liquidity relationship effects on NPM is positive and statistically significant at 1% p-value. This implies that at an increase in liquidity of the selected agribusiness firms, there is an increase on NPM of the selected agribusiness firms. This relationship is obvious as various agribusiness firms depending on the firm's line of business need to be financial capable to meet up with daily business operations. The finding is similar with the findings of Odalo, *et al.* (2016) which found that liquidity has s positive and significant relationship on profitability of agricultural firms listed at the Nairobi securities exchange. The finding supports the findings of Anam and Chaudhry (2019) which found that liquidity among other variables significantly and positively affect the profitability of USA and UK insurance firms which are ancilliary to agribusinesses. The finding contradicts Yildiz, *et al.* (2023) which found a negative effect of liquidity on profitability of Canadian agricultural firms.

The effect of leverage on NPM shows that the coefficient of leverage is -0.085 and with a p-value of 0.381 . Leverage in corporate business connotes the use of external debts to finance business activities. This implies negative relationship and insignificant effect. This is because the p-value of 0.381 is greater than the acceptable p-values range of either of 0.01 , 0.05 and 0.1 . Thus, increase in leverage will simultaneously decrease NPM of the selected agribusinesses. The finding of negative relationship conforms with the findings of Nanda and Panda (2018) which found a negative but significant effect of leverage as a determinant of corporate profitability among listed Indian manufacturing firms between 2000 to 2015. The finding is also in tandem with the findings of Yinusa (2018) which found that short-term leverage among others have negative effect on profitability but is in contrary with the findings of Ajao and Ogieriakhi (2018) which reported an empirically positive and insignificant effect of leverage on profitability of insurance firms quoted in Nigeria stock exchange between 2009 and 2017.

The estimated model finding is:

$$NPM_{it} = \alpha_i(-3.134) + \beta_1(0.015)_{it} + \beta_2(0.579)_{it} + \beta_3(0.252)_{it} + \beta_4(0.470)_{it} + \beta_5(1.219)_{it} + \beta_6(0.405)_{it} + \beta_7(-0.329)_{it} + \beta_8(0.299)_{it} + \beta_9(-0.085)_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The intercept (-3.134) represents the expected value of NPM when macroeconomic and firm-specific variables are not included in the model.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

There is evidence that macro and firm-specific effects affect the profitability of agribusinesses listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange. There is also, a paradigm shift on empiricism using econometric model of fixed effects with Driscoll-Kraay model on profitability research of agribusiness firms listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange (NGX) as portrayed by this study. With this econometric model, effects of macro and firm-specific effects on profitability were unravelled as compared with traditional panel models. The study concludes that macro and firm-specific effects on profitability of agribusiness firms listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange were bank credit and interest rates which were significant macroeconomic variables that positively affect profitability of agribusiness firms as measured by net profit margin, while firm size reduces the net profit margin, liquidity position of the firms increase the net profit margin (profitability) of agribusiness firms

The study recommends based on the levels of significance of the explanatory variables that; financial deepening of expansionary and availability of bank credit, and moderation of interest rates by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should be prioritized as such will increase the profitability of agribusiness firms. The study recommends specifically that agribusiness firms' managements should strategically enforce firm's specific policies of regular assets audit, being prudent in acquiring needed assets, decentralise responsibilities and even create departments or linkages that can contain their expansion as the firms increase in size either by number of employees or large assets holdings to contain unfavourable side effects of increase in size. Finally, liquidity of firms at every production or operation cycle should be prioritized by management to avoid liquidity trap and its detrimental effects.

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